

THE PHENOMENON OF POLYSEMY AS A PHENOMENON OF
LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: This article discusses the phenomenon of polysemy and the lexicological difficulties associated with it. In order to investigate the phenomenon of polysemy, it is necessary to complex definition of this phenomenon. Polysemantic words are analyzed in detail, which have both direct and figurative meaning, as well as tropes - metaphor and metonymy as a means of displaying polysemy. An important role is assigned to the context in the translation and understanding of polysemantic words.

Key words: phenomenon, polysemy, lexicological, difficulties, polysemantic, definition, direct and figurative meaning, metaphor, metonymy, tools, function, context, translation, understanding, words.

The polysemy of a word is an actual linguistic problem, since there are difficulties in understanding the text, which is full of polysemantic words. Many famous linguists such as T.I. Arbekov, S. A. Gorskaya, D.N. Shmelev, L.L. Nelyubin, V.V. Eliseeva, N.B. Gvishiani et al. explore the transmission and interpretation of such vocabulary, find the most optimal linguistic solutions to this problem. The term "polysemy" is translated into Uzbek as *polisemiya* (Greek poly - many, seme -sign). The polysemy of a word means that it can be used in different meanings" [23. S. 172]. V.V. Eliseeva believes that "polysemy, or polysemy of a word, is the presence in a linguistic unit of more than one meaning, provided there is a semantic connection between them or the transfer of common or adjacent specific features or functions from one denotation to another" [9. S. 17]. V.N. Nemchenko explains this "the presence of a unit of language more than one meaning - two or more" [17. S. 281]. D.N. Shmelev writes: "When they talk about polysemy, they mean, first of all, ambiguity words

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as vocabulary units. Lexical polysemy - the ability of one word to serve to designate different objects and phenomena of reality" [28. S. 382]. T.I. Arbekova believes that "many meaning (polysemy) is the ability of a word to serve as a means of naming different classes of objects.

Consequently, the dictionary meanings of a polysemantic word are necessarily different in volume" [2. S. 80]. Of interest is the point of view of I.V. Tolochin, who considers "polysemy" in the denotative but-referential aspect, that is, "In accordance with the idea of the reflective nature correlation concept-word-object, the word has one direct meaning, the center of which is denotate - that is, an object reflected in the mind that exists in external reality as such all other meanings of the word are considered as derived from this basic variant.

All the above definitions reflect the essence of polysemy as a linguistic phenomenon, A polysemic word has several meanings - a denotative (reproducible) meaning and meanings derived from it (contextual). These values form a certain semantic structure and at the same time can be connected in different ways; so many linguists divide the following types of connections between the meanings of polysemantic words: radial, chain and mixed or radial chain. S.A. Gorskaya reveals the essence of each type of connection of polysemantic words: "A radial connection is a connection in which all the meanings of a word are directly related to main" [7. S. 8].

For example flux:

- 1) flow, flow, constant movement, excessive excretion, excessive leakage;
- 2) dysentery; 4) hyperemia; 5) military: second mass, mass flow rate per second;
- 6) magnetic flux; 7) geol.: tide; 8) mech.: rosin; 9) oil: tar; thinner (solid bit; 10) physical-chemical: permeability; specific productivity [29].

"Chain connection is a connection in which each new meaning of a word is connected with the previous one leading, but the "extreme" values may not be related to each other" [7. S. 8].

For example, consider the meanings of the English word - picture:

- 1) a picture consisting of lines and shapes, depicting some kind of object or scene that can be presented in front of a person;
- 2) photograph;
- 3) the image displayed on the TV screen;
- 4) film;
- 5) in British English, the word "picture" denotes a film that delivered to the cinema. American word "movies";

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6) the representation of something in the mind will also be denoted by the word "picture" [29].

It should be noted that the chain connection of polysemantic words in its pure form occurs in language is quite rare, as a rule, in combination with a radial.

"A mixed, or radial-chain connection is a connection of polysemy, when in a word there are both types of communication are accommodated" [7. S. 8]. In practice, radial and mixed lexical of polysemantic words, and chain - edgedot rare. The difficulty of translating polysemy lies in the fact that polysemantic words have a direct and figurative sense in accordance with the names of objects of objective reality. Many linguists attribute such tropes as metaphor, metonymy, and others to the phenomenon of polysemy. "Metaphor-transfer of meaning based on the external similarity of objects or phenomena. hair gold (hair they resemble gold in color and brilliance), the wind howled (the sound resembles the howl of a living being). Metonymy is the transfer of meaning based on the contiguity of objects, phenomena in space or in time. Boil the kettle (i.e., the water in the kettle - we transfer the name vessel on its contents), read Pushkin (works written by A.S. Pushkin), to die in gold (in gold items). A particular type of metonymy is synecdoche - the transfer of naming a part of an object or phenomenon into a whole or a whole into a part: He is the head! (about smart person), a pear (not only a "tree", but also "the fruit of this tree"), a Christmas tree crumbled (not the tree itself, but needles)" [7. S. 84-85]. When translating, it is necessary to take into account that figurative meanings are necessarily containing an associative component. Many words in metaphorical or metonymic transfers meanings are emotionally colored: they predetermine irony, mockery, negligence, disapproval, etc. For example, "lamb (contemptuously about a person who does not know how to stand up for myself); parrot (disrespectful about repeating other people's words); leech (disapproving of those using labor and strength of others); whiskers (kindly about animals: cat, goat, rabbit); a crab (jokingly about a grouch and grumbler). The nature of the emotional coloring is determined by the properties of the objects that make up determine the volume of the original value" [2. S. 84]. Thus, in the aspect of various lexical relations the phenomenon of polysemy can manifest itself in tropes such as metaphor and metonymy in order to give the language an emotional coloring. When understanding or translating such vocabulary, the context plays an important role. Understand what the dictionary meaning should be used in a specific case, the context helps. For example, in the following examples, only context is sufficient to semantize a word: *We decorated the X-*

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tree. He was decorated for a brave deed. Don't lean over the edge of the platform. They stopped at the edge of the forest. It dates him. She dates him. I've got a spoon but there is no fork. He stopped working and stuck the fork into the ground. Sometimes the context does not fulfill its selective function, and the selection of the value is carried out with given the situation. For example, the words *We are going down!*, spoken by the pilot, mean - *We are falling*. But the same words in another situation could mean: *We are sinking or Our position is deteriorating. I didn't hear the report can mean, depending on the situation, I didn't hear the report and I didn't hear the sound of a shot.* If the context and situation do not fulfill their selective function, then the many-valued the word retains its dictionary (lexical) meanings in speech. Intentional preservation of multi-valued is a special stylistic device that evokes additional associations. Using this reception is designed to create a comic effect. For example:

Customer: I would like a book, please.

Bookseller: Something light?

Customer: That does not matter. I have my car with me" [2. S. 83-84].

The contextual meaning of the word entails the question of the concept of "context". As a rule, in speech, the word is used in connection with other words, and not in isolation. Context is the environment the words. A separate sentence in which a particular word is used is often not a context, since the meaning becomes clear only in connection with the previous or subsequent sentence or offers. The context not only reveals the given meaning of the word, but also clarifies and concretizes it, creates a certain circle of associations around it. In the next two examples the word *melon*, used in different contexts, evokes different associations:

1. a melon makes a good breakfast;
2. a melon makes a good missile.

In the first case, the idea of a juicy, sweet and tasty fruit is associated with the word *melon*.

In the second case, an idea arises of its hardness and rounded shape. In both cases the word *melon* is translated by the word "melon", the context does not change the very meaning of the word, but only reveals different sides of the same object [31]. "Contexts, speaking in which the word names objects of different classes, are called different typical. In contexts of different types, different dictionary meanings of the same word are realized.

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Thus, the role of the context is very important in the phenomenon of polysemy, since only thanks to context, it is possible to reveal a certain meaning of the word that arises in connection with its use. The phenomenon of polysemy provides an opportunity to create imagery of speech.

The phenomenon of polysymy as a linguistic phenomenon is very clearly presented in Oscar's novel Wilde's *The Picture of Dorian Gray*. By genre, it is a philosophical man written in a decadent style. Figurative language means occupy an important place in it. They help to better understand the style of the author and understand the meaning of his work. Image system is embodied in the language with the help of lexical figurative and expressive means, in which the word or phrase is used in the converted meaning. Structural Diversity types of images with a certain coarsening is reduced to the principle of metonymy (part or feature instead of whole) and the principle of metaphor (associative conjugation of different objects) [30] (Tables 4, 5).

As can be seen from the table, in fiction there are polysemantic words with radial, chain and mixed bonds are almost equal in number.

Here are some examples:

Radial connection: 1. broken (damaged physically; 2) not working; 3) extremely sad; 4) not as promised/ hoped; 5) not continuous; 6) without hope; 2. to turn (1) change your position; 2) change direction; 3) make circular movement; 4) move page to other side).

Chain connection: 1. a glass (1) clear substance; 2) for drinking out of; 3) objects made of glass; 4) mirror; 5) barometer); 2. a peace (1) a situation in which there is no war between countries or groups;

2) a situation in which people are pleasant and do not cause trouble; 3) a calm quiet situation in which you are not annoyed by noise or other people; 4) a state when you are calm and have no worries).

The author analyze in detail polysemantic words that have both direct and trans nasal meaning, as well as tropes - metaphor and metonymy as a means of displaying polysemy. Important the role in the translation and understanding of polysemantic words is assigned to the context. The work focuses on the need for a comprehensive approach to the study of the phenomenon of polysemy.

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